

A STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF TELEVISION MUSIC BROADCAST ON THE SOCIETY

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Abstract

Since antiquity, music has served several functions as pertains to man and the society he lives in. Music has functioned as a platform for social commentary and information beside other aesthetic purposes. Television music broadcast wields certain positive and negative influences on the society as perceptible in TV viewership in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. It is therefore the aim of this study to examine the degree of impact that television music broadcast has on the individuals of the select region. The research adopts the survey research method. The population of the study includes the entire 276, 800 residents of the select region who are aged eighteen years and above. The major finding of the study reveals among others that there are over thirty-five positive and twenty-five negative influences of television music broadcast on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. There are significant positive influences of television music aired/viewed on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. There are also significant negative influences of television music broadcast on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. The researcher recommends that television music broadcast should be promoted because of the numerous significant positive influences on individuals in the focus area. She also recommends that television music broadcast should be seriously and constantly censored so as to reduce or totally eradicate the negative influences on individuals in Nigeria at large.

Keywords: Television, Music, Broadcast, Influence, Society

Résumé

Une étude de l'influence de la diffusion de musique à la télévision sur la société

Depuis l'antiquité, la musique remplit plusieurs fonctions chez l'homme dans la société où il vit. La musique fonctionne comme plate-forme pour le commentaire et l'information sociale en plus d'autres objectifs esthétiques. La musique diffusée à la télévision exerce certaines influences positives ou négatives sur la société

comme il est le cas dans la zone de Burutu Local Government Area de l'État de Delta. L'objectif de cet article est d'examiner le niveau d'impact que la diffusion de la musique télévisée a sur les individus de la région choisie. La recherche adopte la méthode de sondage. La population de l'étude comprend l'ensemble des 276,800 résidents de la région sélectionnée, âgés de dix-huit ans et plus. Le résultat de l'étude révèle qu'il existe plus de trente-cinq influences positives et vingt-cinq influences négatives de la musique diffusée par la télévision sur les individus dans la zone de Burutu Local Government Area de l'État de Delta. Il y a des influences positives significatives de la musique diffusée à la télévision / regardée par des individus dans la région de Burutu Local Government Area de l'État de Delta. Il existe également des influences négatives importantes de la musique diffusée à la télévision sur les individus dans la zone de Burutu Local Government Area de l'État de Delta. Le chercheur recommande que la diffusion de la musique à la télévision soit encouragée en raison des nombreuses influences positives importantes sur les individus dans le domaine d'intervention. On recommande également que la diffusion de la musique à la télévision soit sérieusement et constamment censurée afin de réduire ou d'éradiquer totalement les influences négatives sur les individus au Nigéria.

Mots-clés : Télévision, Musique, Diffusion, Influence, Société

Introduction

From time immemorial, music has served so many functions ranging from aesthetics to social commentary. It also makes “commentary on the social experience of a given people, and at other times instigates certain reactions among a group of persons. Other functionalities of music include educating and enlightenment and the dissemination of information and culture” (Bartine, 2015, p. 60). The advent of the audio-visual media-the television, provides a platform for music to not only be heard but for its performances and exposure of aspects of cultures to be observed. Sometimes, these performances help interpret the content of the music and have become an integral part of television broadcasts. In the context of this study, television music broadcast, implies all that pertains to music in its visual form which is aired on television. It includes the live performances as well as video clips of musicians on television.

The development of television music broadcast can be traced to what Emenaku (2013) classifies as the fifth period of the emergence of private participation in the development of television broadcasting lasting from 1992 to 2014 with the promulgation of the National Broadcasting Commission (NBC) Decree No. 38 of 1992 by the then Head of State, General Ibrahim Babangida. Furthermore,

Oyeniya (2015) suggests that television broadcasting in present day Nigeria follows three patterns; the traditional, terrestrial, and satellite television broadcasting, such as those aired through DSTV (Multi-choice), MyTV, among others. The new media wave characterized with Facebook, twitter, snapchat and other networking sites have also created spaces for broadcasting in the virtual space.

Television is a powerful electronic media of communication. Digital and analogue television broadcasting have the capacity to affect and shape individuals' and families' cultural values negatively or positively. Television music broadcast to a large extent, influences the psychological development of certain people in the society. Although scholars such as Brewer (2012) contend that there is no observable influence of television music broadcast on the society, other scholars such as Oyeniya (2015) have countered Brewer's position. To Brewer, television music broadcast has the possibility of creating and building positive impact such as entertainment, enhancement of relaxation, which promote psychological comfort for the viewers, knowledge and peace in the society. "It is imperative to note that, television music broadcast also impacts negatively on cultural values through the exposure of indecent dress codes, hair styles, make up, and skin tattoos, which may not be in conformity with traditional African standards" (Emenaku , 2003, p. 134). The portrayal of nudity and use of vulgar languages which are unacceptable to the Nigeria society, have grown to become the attraction of most music broadcast on the television. Such music broadcast has been linked to lots of unlawful and immoral sexual behaviours ranging from verbal sexual expression, erotic touching, masturbation, sex on stage, incest, homosexually and lesbianism, drug abuse, drunkenness, violence, suicide and Satanism.

Chioma (2013) argued that "addiction to television music is time wasting and that the effect of listening to the songs/music with aggressive lyrics is deleterious, demoralising and emotionally destabilising, and should be avoided" (p. 36). While the above submission focuses solely on the limitations of the functionality of the television medium, emphasis is not made on the positive impact of television in the society. To this end, this study examines the positive and negative influences of television music broadcasts on the society, with focus on the residents of Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Influence of Television Music Video Broadcast

As mentioned earlier, television music broadcast is one that serves lots of functions and exerts a variety of influences, both positively and negatively. Okpeki (2017) highlights some positive impacts of television music broadcast in

her unpublished doctoral thesis. She suggests that it contributes to the socio-economic development of individuals and the society at large. She cites examples of the popular Multi-choice music show, MTN Project Fame, wherein live participants gain popularity and amass monetary awards and prizes into their bank accounts. Also, Roberts, Christenson and Gentle (2003) observe that music replaces or invokes the presence of absent peers in order to relate feelings of isolations. In romantic music videos, music is used to create the mood of courtship and sexual behaviour; in friendships, music often provides basis for the initial bond, and offers help to maintain the relationship; in larger gatherings, such as parties, music attracts attention and approval, instigates conversation and encourages dancing. Television music broadcast therefore, serves Nigerians the means of providing information and social interaction. However, Iyorza (2014) warns that vulgar music corrupts morals in children as in the case of banned *Zule Zoo*.

Television music broadcasts, according to Iyorza and Abu (2020), are becoming more interesting to many youths who are inspired to write and produce their own music. Oyeniyi (2015) concurs that “television broadcast has made musicians more popular than they were” (p. 4). This assertion was birthed by the findings from the analysis of the data generated from respondents, which reveal that television music broadcast is a veritable means for identifying and promoting music shows. Abinboge (2013) also cites a number of Nigerian music celebrities who have gained stardom through television reality shows such as Iyanya (Winner of the 2008 MTN Project Fame Reality Show), Chidima Ekile (2010 MTN Project Fame), Omawumi Megbele (First Runner-up, 2007 West Africa Idols), Timi Dakolo (Winner of the 2007 West Africa Idol), Eric Arubaye (Third Runner-up, 2007 West Africa Idol). Television music broadcast exerts much influence on viewers who tend to copy the character, mood and state of the actor and performer, his dress style and expression.

Jaws (1975) and Psycho (1960) cited in Stuart Sisduet (2005), make us understand that music also provides an audience with a vivid, chilling, and classically conditioned associations. Their sheer pitch, melodic or atonality creates numerous feelings in an audience. Television music has become an important medium for providing information to Nigerians. While it serves as a platform for entertainment, sensitive pieces of information are also passed alongside entertainment for instance in the form of jingles. Very often, the Nigerian government uses television music to inform, and orient citizens. The Federal Government of Nigeria, through its Ministry of National Orientation, and the National Television Authority produces’ jingles to educate its citizen. An example of such jingles is presented thus:

Your environment nah your life,
Life de Kule na better environment
Make your environment clean for better better life.
Keep your environment clean.

The above jingle encourages viewers to keep their environment clean. This focuses on environment friendliness. In the same vein, to discourage bush burning, the Nigerian government produced and aired the jingle below:

Fire no be friend, take time use fire.
The better better animals, birds and kamkpe leaf,
root and wood for medicine,
Na di bush we de get them.
Stop bush-burning.
Fire no friend

Bush burning is a reoccurring trend in Nigeria. In fact, the practice has led to the despoliation of the environment. The need to curb bush burning and create an enabling environment for farming and a healthy living, led to the production and airing of the above jingle. The Nigerian Police Public Relations Department also came up with the following:

Criminal no be spirit.
Help police for their work.
Police na your friend.

It is also worthy to mention that television music is used for the enlightenment of citizens and to mobilise them politically. As Ekeira (2014 p.2) asserts, “political mobilisation is a process of sensitising the citizens, increasing their cognition, political consciousness as well as the latter’s efficiency”. Arede (2018) notes that television music is a form of communication which can be used for political advertisement, marketing, campaigns, self-marketing, popular participation and political criticism. From the foregoing, it is evident that the broadcast media in general, when properly utilised, facilitates information flow from the government to the people and can be used to stimulate diverse discussion on national issues and motivate the citizens to participate meaningfully. Okpeki (2017) also examines the value of television music by engaging 254 respondents among the South-Western people of Nigeria. From her investigation, there was a communal mean score of 82, 84 and standard deviation of 20.20. The conclusion indicates that the most broadcast of music on television forms a strong vehicle for the transportation of the socio-cultural values of the South-Western people of Nigeria. This supports Aderemi’s (2017) opinion that virtues and values of the

South-Western people of Nigeria are explored and expressed through their musical genres shown in video clips. He identifies songs about the unity of the people's ideology, the pride of the Yoruba nation, their royalties, religious belief system and the diversity of their craft. Brewer. (2012) similarly holds the view that music brings understanding of one another because it provides a connection in a way that words cannot explain. This is in line with Worugji & Affiah (2016) view that, song has a healing effect on the sufferings of the characters in the play "Some mothers sons". Since every culture creates a unique musical version of life and the sound varies with the personality of the culture and environment in which it evolved, the musical messages of a culture conveys the essence of that social media in a deep and meaningful way.

Nwaolikpe (2013) views the television and other forms of mass media as an important factor in Nigeria with regard to the roles it plays in cultural, educational and national development. Usaini and Ekeanyenaro (2011). In another related study, assert that entertainment television sharpens the social behaviour of teenagers. This happens when they identify a character in the narrative though emotional bond. (Okam, 2016). In their study, they showed a significant relationship between teenagers' frequencies of exposure to and the role of entertainment television programmes in shaping their social behaviour, even though the influences may be either negative or positive.

In spite of the numerous benefits of television music, there are equally multiple negative influences on the individuals and the society at large. As Okpeki (2017) notes, criticism aimed at current popular music stems from the assumption that its content which include attitudes, values, and behaviours etc, portrayed may influence how viewers/listeners think and act. Degradation of cultural and traditional values in preference for Western values is another negative influence recorded. Western values according to Culz (2015) has eaten deep into the fabrics of Nigerian cultures and traditions. This debasement has translated to erotic imagery, promiscuity instead of chastity, anti-social behavior, gang related violence, armed robbery etc a daily basis. School of thought. Also, Worugji (2010) discussed the needed change in Western values against positive cultural values in Nigeria. The ideas expressed are in line with the focus of this study.

Methodology

The design of this study is a Cross Sectional survey research design. This method is considered appropriate because, the study involves data collection with the aid of questionnaire from respondents in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The population of the study represents the entire 276, 800 people

in Burutu Local Government Area according to the National Population Commission (2012).

The sample for this study is drawn from the population based on the Yamane (1964) sample size determination formula. The formula is given as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + Ne^2}$$

where: N = population size, n= sample size, 1 = constant, e = error limit margin of error of level of significance

The Yamane (1964) sample size of determination is used with the multistage sampling technique.

Thus, out of the 52 communities that make up Burutu Local Government Area, 11 communities were systematically picked from the 11 wards. Each of the selected communities were allocated 36 respondents, where the extra four respondents were systematically allocated to Torugbene, Ojobo, Ekiagbodo and Newtown being the major towns. With the application of the multi-stage sampling, male and female respondents, who are 18 years and above, were selected from each of the identified communities.

The study used the descriptive statistics, frequencies, percentages, mean scores and standard deviation in interpreting the data collected from the field to answer the research questions and inferential statistics. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) R-squared, and the T-test were used in testing the hypotheses formulated for the study. For the inferential statistics, data were transformed from nominal to ordinal for easy measurement of the variables using the International Business Machine (IBM) SPSS statistics version 20 and Excel Spreadsheet 2016 version.

The survey in this study was conducted using a structured questionnaire as the main instrument for data collection. The structure of the questions, designed in a close-ended format, required the respondents to choose from a list of options. The instrument is made up of two sections: the socio-demographic section covering items on sex, age, educational qualification, etc and the thematic section relating to the influence of television music broadcast on individuals and the society.

In this study, the validity of the instrument was observed by adhering to the self-evident measures, classified as face and content validity. In ensuring face validity the structured questionnaire was subjectively assessed by experts in departments

of Music and Communication Arts, Delta State University, Abraka to confirm the relevance of the questions and coherence. They critically evaluated the question and made suggestions which were adopted. Content validity was ascertained by comprehensively examining the scope it was intended to measure. The relevant content, guiding the achievement of the study's objectives were reviewed and included in the questionnaire.

In testing for the reliability of the instrument, the test-retest method was applied through a pilot survey test conducted using 30 respondents from 8 Community in Delta State who were not part of the sample size. A re-test was also carried out after 2 weeks of the initial test. Scores derived from both tests were correlated to find the stability of the instrument over a period of time, using Cronbach Alpha reliability test. The result of the pilot test shows an alpha value of 0.89 which is found to be consistent, therefore, the instrument is deemed reliable. The copies of the questionnaire were administered by the researcher with the aid of two trained research assistants with a close monitoring of the outcome of retrieved data to the respondents. This is because the researcher aimed to ensure no mutilation, early and high return rate. A total of 400 questionnaires were administered to respondents, out of which 378 were returned accurately filled.

Presentation and Analysis of Results

Research Question 1: What are the types of television station frequently viewed in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of types of television stations frequently viewed in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria

S/N	Types of televisions status frequently viewed	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	African Independent Television (AIT)	378	3.16	58	+
2	Channels Television	378	3.32	73	+
3	Delta Broadcasting Service (DBS)	378	3.30	67	+
4	Independent Television (ITV) Benin	378	3.16	67	+
5	Nigerian Television Authority (Sapele) Benin, Port-Harcourt	378	3.37	52	+
6	Silberbird Television	378	3.42	54	+
7	Trance Television	378	3.68	62	+
8	Trybe television	378	3.18	73	+
9	Trib television	378	3.42	48	+
10	Star Times television	378	3.32	66	+
11	Sole music television	378	3.32	52	+
12	Pilariot television	378	3.30	68	+
13	Sound City television	378	3.16	76	+
14	E-channel television	378	3.42	52	+
15	Hit television	378	3.68	48	+
16	Multi-choice African (DSTV/GO TV)	378	3.18	66	+
17	My TV	378	3.42	52	+
18	Channel O	378	3.16	54	+
19	Kenya Music television	378	3.32	62	+
20	Murhi television	378	3.30	73	+
Grand Mean =			3.33		

Source: Field Work 2020

Table 1 is presentation and analysis of responses to research question 1 on the types of television stations frequently viewed in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. The table reveals that respondents' reactions have their mean scores all above the acceptance bench mark of 2.50. The indication of this is that the 20 items are all types of television stations frequently viewed in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State of Delta State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What are the types of music frequently aired from television stations in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation on types of music frequently aired from television stations in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State Nigeria

S/N	Types of music frequently aired from television stations	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Reggae	378	3.42	54	+
2	Country	378	3.68	62	+
3	Highlife	378	3.18	73	+
4	Blues	378	3.42	48	+
5	Cultural/traditional music	378	3.32	66	+
6	Christian music	378	3.32	52	+
7	Hip-hop	378	3.30	68	+
8	Afro beat	378	3.16	76	+
9	Classical	378	3.42	52	+
10	Rap	378	3.68	48	+
11	Ginggles	378	3.42	54	+
12	RM & B	378	3.56	64	+
Grand Mean:			3.41		

Source: Field Work 2020

Table 2 is presentation and analysis of responses to research question 2 on the types of music frequently aired from television stations in Burutu Local Government Area. The table reveals that respondents have their mean scores all above the acceptance bench mark of 2.50. The indication of this is that the 12 items were all types of music frequently aired from television stations in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Research Question 3: What are the positive influences of television music on individual and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean and standard deviation on the positive influences of television music in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria

S/N	Positive influences of television music	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Creates and cement social relations	378	3.42	48	+
2	Provides cultural and traditional knowledge	378	3.32	66	+
3	Provides aesthetics pleasure	378	3.32	52	+
4	Sexual stimulant	378	3.30	68	+
5	Occupy the idol hand	378	3.16	76	+
6	Creates popularity	378	3.42	52	+
7	Gives economic returns	378	3.16	58	+
8	Invoke the presence of absent peers	378	3.32	73	+
9	Enjoyment of enhanced stardom	378	3.30	62	+
10	Accompaniment for courtship	378	3.16	67	+
11	Provides the basis for the initial bonds	378	3.37	50	+
12	Maintain relationship	378	3.42	54	+
13	Used for cultural attention and approval	378	3.30	68	+
14	Provides types of conversation	378	3.16	76	+
15	Encourages dancing with therapeutic values	378	3.42	52	+
16	Provision of information	378	3.68	48	+
17	Social interaction	378	3.40	54	+
18	Serves educational purposes	378	3.42	48	+
19	Provides entertainment	378	3.32	66	+
20	Provides orientation	378	3.32	52	+
21	Used for moral training	378	3.30	68	+
22	Used as satire	378	3.37	50	+
23	For national development	378	3.42	54	+
24	Builds understanding of others and groups	378	3.30	68	+
25	Gratification-satisfaction of needs	378	3.32	55	+
26	Socio-economic and political enlightenment	378	3.40	68	+
27.	Socio-economic and political	378	3.16	58	+

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	mobilization				
28.	Creates avenues for reflection	378	3.32	73	+
29.	Help to define oneself	378	3.30	62	+
30.	Provides trends in fashion	378	3.16	67	+
31.	Sparks up sense of creativity	378	3.38	72	+
32.	It serves as voice of the community	378	3.68	48	+
33.	It serve as voice of the individual	378	3.40	54	+
34.	A unifying factors/social bond	378	3.42	48	+
35.	Mnemonic device aiding memorability and product recall	378	3.32	66	+
Grand Mean =			3.34		

Source: Field Work 2020

Table 3 is presentation and analysis of responses to research question 3 on the Positive influences of television music in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The table reveals that respondents have their mean scores all above the acceptance bench mark of 2.50. The indication of this is that the 35 items were all Positive influences of television music in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: What are the negative influences of viewing television music in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Mean and standard deviation on negative influences of viewing television music in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria?

S/N	Negative influence of viewing television music	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1	Obnoxious scene	378	3.16	58	+
2	Violence	378	3.32	73	+
3	Sexism	378	3.30	62	+
4	Nudity/indecent exposure of body parts	378	3.16	67	+
5	Use of vulgar language	378	3.37	50	+
6	Drug abuse	378	3.42	54	+
7	Gangsterism	378	3.30	68	+
8	Smoking	378	3.16	76	+
9	Suicide	378	3.42	52	+
10	Disrespect for elders	378	3.32	55	+
11	Disloyalty to authority	378	3.40	68	+
12	Troublesome attitude	378	3.36	52	+
13	Recklessness	378	3.38	50	+

14	Gender bias	378	3.42	54	+
15	Male chauvinism	378	3.30	68	+
16	Depression	378	3.32	55	+
17	Deliberate infliction of harm	378	3.40	68	+
18	Leads to outright murder	378	3.42	54	+
19	Degradation of cultural/traditional value	378	3.30	68	+
20	Vicarious behaviour	378	3.32	55	+
21	Promiscuity	378	3.40	68	+
22	Addiction	378	3.36	52	+
23	Time wasting	378	3.38	50	+
24.	Corruption of the mind	378	3.42	54	+
25.	Health problems to the eyes	378	3.30	68	+
Grand Mean			3.34		

Source: Field Work 2020

Table 4 is presentation and analysis of responses to research question 4 on the Negative/disadvantages of viewing television music in Burutu L.G.A. The table reveals that respondents' reactions have their mean scores all above the acceptance bench mark of 2.50. The indication of this is that the 25 items are all Negative influences of viewing television music in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There are no significant positive influences of television music aired/viewed on individuals on the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Test of positive significant influences of television music aired/viewed on individuals and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria

Number N = 378		Positive influence of television music aired/viewed
Television music	Pearson r	0.947
	r Squared	0.90
	t-value	92.66
	P-value	0.000
	DF	376

Significant level (P < 0.05)

Source: Field Work, 2020

The table shows the test of significant positive influences of television music aired/viewed on individuals and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. The table shows r-0.947 indicates a 95% positive influences of television music aired/viewed on individuals in the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

To measure the strength of the influences, the coefficient of determination (r – squared) value = 0.90 which implies 90% of the variance in the influences.

To test if the influences were significant or not, the fisher r – t test formula was used with the formula

$$t = r \sqrt{\frac{n-2}{1-r^2}} \quad \text{where } r = \text{correlation coefficient, } n = \text{sample size at 5\% level of significance}$$

Arising from above, the observed t-value = 92.66 with a probability value of 0.000. Therefore, it indicates that the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate hypothesis accepted.

Ho2: There are no negative significant influences of television music on individuals and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Test of negative significant influences of television music on individuals and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Number N = 378		Negative influences of television music aired/viewed
Television music	Pearson r	0.842
	Television music	0.71
	r-value	49.06
	P-value	0.000
	Df	376

Significant level (P < 0.05)

Source: Field Work, 2020

Table shows the test of negative significant influences of television music on individuals and the society. We observed that r = 0.842 which indicates 84% influences. However, the strength of the influences was measured using the

coefficient of determination (r-squared) value = 0.71. To test if the influences were significant, the fisher r-to-t test formula was used at 5% level of significance. This yielded observed t-value of 49.06 with a probability value of 0.000, with the degree of freedom at 376. Consequently the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternate accepted i.e. there were negative significant influences of television music on individuals and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

The first finding arises from research question 1 on the television stations frequently viewed in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State. Table 1 indicates that television stations frequently viewed include: African Independent Television, Channels Television, Delta Broadcasting Service (DBS), Independent Television (ITV) Benin, Nigerian Television Authority (Sapele) Benin, Silverbird Television, Trance Television, Trybe Television, Trib Television, Star Times Television, Sole Music Television, Pilariot Television, Sound City Television, E-channel Television, Hit Television, Multi-choice African (DSTV/GOTV), My Television, Channel O, Kenya Music Television, and Murhi Television. This finding supports the works of Okpeki (2017) who also listed these stations as available television stations in Western Nigeria which include Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

The second finding comes from the data gathered from research question 2 on the types of music frequently aired which include: Reggae, Country, Highlife, Blues, Cultural/traditional music, Christian music, Hip-hop, Afro beat, Classical, Rap, Jingles, R&B. This supports the research of Nwaolikpe (2013) Usani and Ekeanyonwu (2011).

The third finding was generated from responses to research question 3 on the positive influence of television music on the individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The finding identified include the following: It creates and cements social relations, provides cultural and traditional knowledge, provides aesthetic pleasure, sexual stimulant and also creates popularity Also, it gives economic returns, invokes the presence of absent peers, enjoyment of enhanced stardom, accompaniment of courtship, provides the basis for the initial bonds, maintains relationship and it is used for cultural attention and approval. In the same vein, it also encourages dancing with therapeutic value, the provision of information, social interaction, serves educational purposes, provides entertainment, provides orientation and also used for moral training. Furthermore, it is used as satire, for national development, builds understanding of others and groups, the gratification-satisfaction of needs,

socio-economic, and political enlightenment, and political mobilization. It creates an avenue for reflection, helps to define one, provides trends in fashion, speaks up sense of creativity, serves as voice of the community, serves as a unifying factor/social bond, and serves as a mnemonic device by aiding memory and product recall.

This finding is in agreement with the finding of Usani and Ekeanyanwu (2011), Nwaolikpe (2013), Oyeniyee (2015), Okpeki (2015) and Aderemi (2017). Also, the test of hypothesis on table 4 reveals, that there are significant positive influences of television music on the individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The finding supports that of Johnson (2007), Ariye (2010), Olusoti (2013) that television music plays important roles in people and a society's everyday life.

The fourth finding was generated from responses from research question 4 on the negative influences of television music on individuals and the society in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. This is exemplified in table 4 as obnoxious scenes, violence, sexism, nudity/indecent exposure of body parts, use of vulgar language, drug abuse, gangsterism, smoking, suicide, disrespect for elders, disrespect for elders, disloyalty to authority, troublesome attitude, recklessness, gender bias, male chauvinism, depression, deliberate infliction of harm, degradation of cultural/traditional value, promiscuity, negative addiction, time wastage, corruption of the mind, and health problems to the eyes and others.

The test of hypothesis 2 also indicates that there are significant negative influences of television music broadcast on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. This supports the works of Ariye (2010), Onobajo (2015) Chioma (2013), Okpeki (2015), Thomas, Marca Bronninmann, Frinkel, Ehtert and Nater (2013, II), that television music broadcast also has so many negative influences on individuals and the society with some obnoxious contents.

Summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations

This research has examined the influences of television music broadcast on the society, with particular focus on viewers in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria. The study utilized the cross sectional survey research design. The population of the study represents the entire 276, 800 people in Burutu Local Government Area according to the National Population Commission (2012). This was made up of citizens that are eighteen (18) years of age and above. This Yamane (2014) sample size determination formula was also

used alongside the multi-stage sampling technique to sample 400 respondents. However, only 378 questionnaires were returned.

The questionnaire was the main instrument used. The descriptive statistics of frequency percentages, means and standard deviation were also adopted in interpreting the data collected. The Pearson product moment and correlational coefficient were used with the t-test statistic in testing the hypotheses formulated. The findings reveal that there are:

1. Over thirty-five (35) positive influences of television music broadcast on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.
2. Over 25 negative influences of television music broadcast on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.
3. Significant positive influences of television music aired/viewed on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.
4. Significant negative influences of television music broadcast on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria.

Conclusion

Music is a veritable medium of transformation, knowledge and information dissemination, entertainment, socio-economic and political mobilization, enlightenment, and advertisement, which positively influences the society. With over thirty-five (35) positive influences of television music broadcast as against twenty-five (25) negative influences recorded in this study, the research concludes that the positive influence of television music outweighs the negative influence. The research recommends that television music broadcast should be promoted because of the numerous significant positive influences on individuals and the society, television music broadcast should be seriously and constantly censored so as to reduce or totally eradicate the negative influences on individuals in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria in particular and Nigeria at large. Thus helping us to avert what Okam and Ozumba (2020) have captioned "' Wish we had tried harder'".

References

- Adeniyi, W. (2015). Top ten dance styles in Nigeria: Plus dance tutorial videos. Internet: <https://www.thenews.ng>. Retrieved November 1, 2015.
- Aderemi, S.A. (2009). Yoruba nationalism: culture, politics and violence in South-Western Nigeria (1900-2009). <https://www.ifeas.uni-main2.de>. Retrieved Monday 06, 2016.
- Anderson, C.A. and Eubanks J. (2003). Exposure to violent media: The effects of songs with violent lyrics on Aggressive thoughts and feeling. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* vol. 84(5) 960-971.
- Anho J.E. (2018). *Television music as a tool for political enlightenment and mobilization*. A Seminar paper delivered at media week programme. Department of Mass Communication, Delta State University, Abraka.
- Arede, E. (2018). *Influence of radio broadcasting on political mobilization in Burutu Local Government Area of Delta State*. Benin: Idodo Umeh Publishers.
- Ariye, E.C. (2010). The impact of private broadcasting in Nigeria'. *Pakistan Journal of Social Sciences*. Vol. 7(6) 415-423.
- Bartine, D. (2015). The Contrapuntal Humanisms of Edward Said. *Interdisciplinary Literary Studies*. Vol. 17, (1): 59-85.
https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.5325/intelitestud.17.1.0059?seq=1&cid=pdfreference#references_tab_contents
- Brewer, C. (2012). *Using music to carry the message of learning*. www.songforteaching.com. Retrieved Friday June 3rd, 2015.
- Chioma, P.E. (2013). Television local contents: conduct for cultural learning in Nigeria? *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review* Vol. 2(12):26-40.
- Curts, C.N. (2018). The traditional and cultural values on valued: The case of media effects on the society. <http://www.valuesaresacred.c>. downloaded 2018.
- Ekeria, J.E. (2016). The role of women groups and association in political mobilization. An unpublished Bachelor of Arts Project Department of Mass Communication, University of Benin, Benin City.
- Ekhayeme G. (2011). The Influence of Television on Family Institution in Nigeria. www.bonnors.online.

- Ekwueme, L.E.N. (1993). Nigeria music since independence. *The economic and social science journal* (6): 320-331.
- Emenaku, S. (2003). The deregulation of the Nigerian broadcast industry and the ensuring challenges and opportunities. In Akinfeleye, R.A. and Okoye, I.E. (eds.) *Issues in Nigeria media history: 1900, 2000AI*, Lagos: Malthouse Press Limited. Pp. 134-146.
- Iyorza, S. (2014). Quality Issues and the Ban on Selected Musical Video Broadcasting in Nigeria: A Defence for National Broadcasting Commission. *Nigerian Theatre Journal*.13.2. Pp 172-183.
- Iyorza, S. & Abu, P. (2020). "Nigerian Television Drama Series and Audience Reactions: A Seismology Evaluation." *Jurnal Sosialisasi: Jurnal Hasil Pemikiran, Penelitian dan Pengembangan Keilmuan Sosiologi Pendidikan*. 1.1. Pp. 47-54. <https://ojs.unm.ac.id/sosialisasi>
- Johnson, B. & Christensen, L. (2007). Educational researcher quantitative, qualitative and mixed research. Downloaded from www.southalabama.edu. 10th October, 2016.
- Nwaolikpe, O.N. (2013). Nigerian television authority: A brief history. Internet: nigerianfinder.com. Retrieved Friday May 06, 2016.
- Ogunrinade D.O.A. (2013). Corruption reduction in Nigeria: Appraisal of the Role of Music Mediterranean *Journal of Social Sciences*. 4(1).
- Okam, C.L. (2016). The Convergence of Popular Theatre, Entertainment Education and Theatre for Development in the Performing Arts Discipline. *COJOTH Journal of Theatre and Humanities*. Vols. 2, Nos 2&3 May 2016. Pp23-39.
- Okam, C.L & Ozumba N.L. (2020). "...Wish we had tried Harder": Post Pandemic Nigeria. Administrative and Communication Frugality on Covid-19. *Ndunode*, Vol 17, No 1, January 2020. Pp. 1-14.
- Okpeki, P.I. (2017). The Evolution of television music in southern western Nigeria: 1959-2014. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis, Faculty of Arts, Delta State University, Abraka.
- Olusoji, S (2015). The relevance of music education to the Nigerian system. *African Journal of Teachers Education*, vol. 3 (1).

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- Oluwadahunsi, O. (2015). Nudity in Nigerian music videos. Internet: nationalmirroronline.net. pg: 1:7, Retrieved Wednesday November 23rd, 2015.
- Onabajo, F. (2005). Promoting indigenous culture and community life in Nigeria through the Mass Media Studies in Tribes Tribals, vol. 3(2):93-98.
- Oyeniya, S. (2015). Top 7 Nigerian musicians who got famous through reality television shows. Internet: thesheet.ng. Retrieved Friday November 27, 2015.
- Roberts, D.F. Christenson P.G., and Gentile D.A. (2008). Effects of violent music on children and adolescents.
- Seidman, R. (2013). List of how many homes each cable networks is in-cable network coverage estimates as at August 2013”. Retrieved November 24th 2015.
- Staurt, D. (2012). Why do NPR shows take music interlude “break”? Internet: <http://www.quora.com>. Retrieved November 9, 2015.
- Thoma, M.V. , Morca, R.I. Bronnimann, R. Finkel, I., Ehlert, U; and Nater, U.M. (2013). The effect of music on the human stress responses. Rockville, U.S.A.: National centre for Biotechnology Information, U.S. National Library of Medicine. Internet: www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov. Retrieved Friday November 20th, 2015.
- Usani, S. & Ekeanyanwu, N.T. (2011). Perceived role of entertainment television in shaping social behaviour of teenagers. *The journal of the African council for communication education (ACCE)*, Nigeria chapter vol. 9(1): 154=182.
- Worugji, G.E. (2010). A call for change: traditional African values and modern Africa in the play, *The broken calabash* by Tess Osonye Onwueme. *Lwatt. A Journal of Contemporary Research*, 7.(4), 100-106. ISSN: 1813-2227.
- Worugji, G.E & Uwem A. (2016). Maltreatment, greed and self-centeredness in Myke Van Gram’s play, *Some mothers sons*. *Lwati: A Journal of contemporary Research*, 13.(2),39-47. ISSN: 1813-2227.